

ANNUAL REPORT

2024-2025

CLIR

Council on Library &
Information Resources

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MESSAGE FROM THE PRESIDENT

Enduring Perspectives

With each annual report, CLIR presents current programs and projects that exemplify our mission and reflect our vision in service to a durable and accessible cultural heritage. During the last few decades we have worked with colleagues focused on varieties of cultural expression that are hidden from public view or threatened by the exigencies of climate change. In these instances CLIR provides the services and expertise to make visible and secure what otherwise would be lost. Accordingly, this year we highlight ongoing work on behalf of Hidden Collections Africa, emerging projects such as our formal partnership with the Integral Ecology Research Network at the University of Oxford, and ongoing programs such as Recordings at Risk and Digitizing Hidden Collections: Amplifying Unheard Voices.

This year we also approach a milestone: CLIR’s 70th anniversary spans the years 2026 and 2027. To flourish for seven decades is itself an accomplishment worth noting. In the coming months, we will comb our archives for notable contributions, insights, and projects that show the evolution—and continuity—of CLIR’s original mandate to preserve and make accessible knowledge integral to the public good.

CLIR’s origin story is instructive. The Council was inaugurated to cooperatively effect a better professional response to a poorly managed, redundant, and expensive explosion of information—the 1950s brought microfilm and microfiche,

exponential growth in academic book publishing and a surge of new journals, and the rise of television as a chief source of narrating world events and our place in it. Against this backdrop, the potential loss of information due to outdated methods of curation and preservation presented real threats to the futures of research and learning.

Those distant concerns parallel our contemporary focus on better managing the wild proliferation of digital information and data, a nearly ubiquitous but poorly understood adoption of artificial intelligence as, in many instances, a tool we substitute for our acumen and allow to “speak” for us, and the still pervasive threat of at-risk culture in a Pandora’s media.

DLF Forum, Michigan State University. July 2024

We will also attempt to place CLIR in the current zeitgeist—a roiled and unpredictable space and time as of this writing—and postulate, however misty our lens, what may lie ahead.

Contemplating our relative longevity, certain perspectives come to mind that have guided us through the latter half of the 20th century and well into the 21st: “perspectives” in the sense of ways of seeing, frameworks of reference that provide for a broader understanding of the world, translating across generations and historical periods punctuated by shifting norms and often jarring disruptions. These are vital conceptual guides for interpreting and structuring our response to present “wicked” challenges:

Human rights. CLIR’s programs and projects assume that all people have a protected right to knowledge, a right to participate in one’s culture of choice, and a right to education. In recent years we have cited specifically the Universal Declaration of Human Rights published in 1948 in the aftermath of World War II as the framework for much of our work. The Declaration is as urgent now as it was when adopted.

Complexity. The founders of the Council understood the tsunami of new information in 1957 as one aspect of a very expensive crisis. A second element contributing to the crisis was a mindset within higher education that prized strongly independent institutions that act competitively and uncooperatively, prompted by incentives for institutional growth and status rivalry (rankings, prestige). There was nothing that the Council could do to staunch the information explosion. The real challenge was instilling a new frame of reference whereby the academic institutions would understand the crisis as systemic and warranting a collaborative, interdependent resolution. Seeing our workplace through the lens of a complex system has proven core to CLIR’s mission ever since.

Treaty 8 Tribal Association, Grant Recipient
Amplifying Unheard Voices

Community. To adequately address complex challenges, we have since inception believed that remedial action is best realized through collaborative relationships. Communities of purpose and practice are essential to a sustainable cultural heritage. CLIR facilitates these functioning networks through shared research publications, regranting programs, digital libraries, memoranda of understanding, affiliations, professional development and leadership programs, and fellowships. When successful, these efforts help shape a social unit defined by cohesiveness and mutual interest and—at best—a publicly minded spirit.

Hope. CLIR accepts hope as a sophisticated cognitive strategy, a state of mind based on expectations of positive changes in events or circumstances in life and the world at large. Hope inspires us to adjust the focus of our human agency and our place in the world in order to effect different, more salutary outcomes in the face of prevailing detrimental forces. Transformative hope requires the perception of a temporal continuity: drawing upon experience and knowledgeable insight (that occurred in the past) selectively reconstituted as a series of steps and purposeful iterations (performed in a progressive present)

that can then be imaginatively applied to a subsequent reality (future) and, if successful, instantiate that future. We try to develop working environments that allow for hope to flourish.

These perspectives are intertwined. They require long term dedication, and they require an optimism that human agency that embraces diversity of thought and equitable ends is within our collective reach. Going on 70 years, for educational, cultural and memory institutions and professions in service to the common good, CLIR has and will continue to advance adaptive, consilient praxis; to ameliorate the fractures of our unsettled times, we work together: an applied harmony.

DLF

DIGITAL LIBRARY FEDERATION

DLF Forum, Michigan State University. July 2024

A program of CLIR, the Digital Library Federation (DLF) advances research, learning, social justice and the public good through the creative design and wise application of digital library technologies. Through vibrant and active **working groups**, the DLF community develops guidelines for best practices, creates **toolkits** and other openly available **resources**, conducts research, and builds cross-organization networks of practitioners with common interests and challenges. Member organizations receive access to community news, a job board, and discounts for professional development opportunities such as the program’s signature event—the DLF Forum.

The DLF Forum brings together digital library, archives, and museum professionals from around the country and the world. In 2024, DLF convened two Forums: an in-person conference at Michigan State University in July and the 2024 Virtual Forum in October.

DLF 2024 FORUM

Featured Speakers

DLF Forum in-person

Kathleen Fitzpatrick

Germaine Halegoua

Andrea Jackson Gavin
Program Director, HBCU Trust
and featured speaker
2024 Virtual Forum

2024 In-Person DLF Forum

Michigan State University

July 29-31, 2024

- Registration: 190
- Speakers: 56
- Countries represented: Canada, Egypt, Mexico, Norway, the United Kingdom, and the US (34 states and Washington, DC)
- First-time participants: 50%

2024 Virtual Forum

Zoom Events

October 22-23, 2024

- Registration: 695
- Speakers: 102
- Sponsor representatives: 14
- Presentation breakdown: 14 presentations; 9 panel sessions; 5 working sessions; 4 workshops; 3 wellness break sessions

DLF

HIGHLIGHTS

July 2024: The Born-Digital Access Working Group (BDAWG) was awarded a Strategic Growth Grant from the Society of American Archivists Foundation. The grant has supported a study to investigate how members of the US archival community are utilizing AI and machine learning to enhance access to digital materials.

August 2024: The Society of American Archivists Council honored the BDAWG working group with an Exemplary Service Award, citing the group’s “robust, forward-looking community of practice focused on ensuring that cultural heritage institutions are equipped and able to provide access to the born-digital materials in their care.”

September 2024: The Climate Justice Working Group launched the Climate Resiliency Action Series, a new community of practice focused on addressing climate change in libraries and cultural heritage institutions. Recordings and documentation of the series are available on the project website, <https://climate-resiliency.clir.org/>.

January 2025: DLF announced the creation of the new Digitization Interest Group, a community of practice for discussion and learning about evolving standards, workflows, and technologies for digitization.

DLF

WORKING GROUPS 2024-2025

DLF Forum, Michigan State University. July 2024

- Arts and Cultural Heritage Working Group
- Assessment Interest Group
- Born-Digital Access Working Group
- Climate Justice Working Group
- Committee for Equity and Inclusion
- Data & Digital Scholarship Working Group
- Digital Accessibility Working Group
- Digital Library Pedagogy Group
- Digitization Interest Group
- Linked Open Data Zotero Group
- Metadata Support Group
- Project Managers Group
- Technology Strategy for Archives Working Group
- Working Group on Labor in Digital Libraries

GRANT PROGRAMS

In 2024–2025, CLIR’s two national regranting programs facilitated the digitization of rare and unique collections, significantly expanding public access to hidden histories and ensuring the preservation of culturally significant materials.

Community members advocating for democracy and unity in Fiji in 1987[?], Vancouver, BC. South Asian Canadian Digital Archive (SACDA), Chandra Bodalia fonds.

Digitizing Hidden Collections: Amplifying Unheard Voices is a grant competition for digitizing rare and unique content stewarded by nonprofit organizations in the US and Canada. Grant recipients digitize materials that deepen public understanding of the histories of people of color and other communities and populations whose work, experiences, and perspectives have been insufficiently recognized or unattended. Between 2022 and 2025, CLIR issued 2 calls for proposals, awarding \$8 million for 33 projects. In February 2025, CLIR announced the receipt of a \$5 million grant from the Mellon Foundation. This grant will make possible a fourth award cycle to take place in 2025-2026.

Iowa Conservation Commission Collection Films, State Historical Society of Iowa.

Recordings at Risk supports the preservation of rare and unique audio, audiovisual, and other time-based media of public value. By funding digital reformatting, the program helps ensure these materials are safeguarded for future generations and made accessible to researchers, educators, and communities. Between 2017 and 2025, CLIR issued 11 calls for proposals, awarding \$5.96 million for 190 projects. As of 2025, the program has made possible the digital reformatting of more than 59,000 recordings held in collecting organizations across the US.

AWARDS GRANTED, 2024-2025

Digitizing Hidden Collections: Amplifying Unheard Voices

- American Folk Art Museum, *Continuing Care: Digitizing the Healing Arts Initiative (HAI) Archive*, \$273,121
- Columbus Metropolitan Library; Kings Art Complex, *Digitizing the Columbus Call & Post Photo Archive: Voices of Historic Black Columbus*, \$241,406
- Historic Hudson Valley, *Voices from the Archives: Digitizing Historic Hudson Valley's Manuscript Collection to Broaden Access to Insights on the Lives of Women and Enslaved Individuals in New York*, \$137,735
- Kehkimin, *Kehkimin-Wolastoqey Educational Media Player*, \$125,700
- Law College Association; Navajo Nation Department of Water Resources; Law Library Microform Consortium; Agnese Nelms Haury Program in Environment and Social Justice, *Navajo Nation Department of Water Resources Library Preservation Project*, \$300,000
- Mississippi State University Libraries, *Freedom Means: Digitizing the Hidden Stories of Black Mississippians' Fight for Civil Rights*, \$123,403
- Oregon Historical Society; Densho, *Citizen(s) Yasui: Illuminating the Japanese American Experience through the Yasui Family Collections*, \$298,934
- Rennie Harris American Street Dance Archive, *The Fifth Element: Surfacing Oral and Embodied Histories of Hip-hop and Street Dance*, \$180,000
- San Diego State University Chicana/o Studies and Special Collections, *Unearthing the Chicana/o Movement in San Diego: Digitizing the Education Movimiento*, \$300,000
- Six Nations Public Library; Royal Ontario Museum, *Clippings: Indigenous Writings, Settler Colonial Representations in the Newspaper Scrapbooks of the Royal Ontario Museum, Digitally Rematriated to the Six Nations of the Grand River*, \$256,496
- South Asian Studies Institute; The Royal BC Museum; Sikh Heritage Museum; Poetic Justice Foundation, *Histories of South Asians in Canada: A Visual Ethnographic Documentation of Chandra Bodalia*, \$299,995
- Texas Archive of the Moving Image, *Reclaiming and Sharing LGBTQ+ History from the KPRC-TV Houston Collection*, \$68,641
- Treaty 8 Tribal Association, *Digital Repatriation of the Ridington Dane-zaa Archive*, \$291,901
- The University of Akron Archives & Special Collections, *Digitizing the Photographs of Horace and Evelyn Stewart, 1897-1978*, \$190,517
- University of Minnesota Libraries, *Community Celebration of Place: Intergenerational, cross-cultural histories from the Larry Long papers*, \$299,843
- University of Nebraska-Lincoln Libraries; Malone Community Center, *Recovering Lost Stories: Digitizing the history of the Malone Community Center, the heartbeat of an "invisible" Black community in Lincoln, Nebraska*, \$235,197
- University of Victoria Libraries, *trans(formation): Digitizing the Rikki Swin Institute Trans+ activism and outreach media collection*, \$289,218
- Wing Luke Museum of the Asian Pacific American Experience, *Digitization of materials related to Chinese laborers and merchants seeking admission to the United States, 1894-1921 & additional materials related to Chinese Exclusion Act in Pacific Northwest*, \$62,000

AWARDS GRANTED, 2024-2025

Recordings at Risk

- American Craft Council, *The Voice of American Craft*, \$38,268
- American Jewish Archives, *The Global Voice of the Jewish Community: Saving the Films of B'nai B'rith International*, \$43,985
- Amherst Center for Russian Culture, *Voices of Soviet Theater History: Digitizing the Alma Law Collection*, \$49,929
- Austin Film Festival, *Austin Film Festival Presents On Story*, \$47,549
- Chicago City Clerk's Office, *Digitizing the Chicago City Council Audio Recordings*, \$38,260
- Chicago Film Archives, *Small Gauge, Big Shoulders: Digitizing Bill Stamets' Super-8 Magnetic Sound Films of Public Life in Chicago*, \$44,450
- The City College of New York – Dominican Studies Institute, *Preserving Dominican Bachata Voices: Digitizing the Deborah Pacini Hernández Music Collection*, \$17,082
- Hammond Castle Museum, *Hammond Castle Museum Recordings*, \$14,547
- Illinois State Archives, *Reformatting the Audio Recordings of the Illinois Legislative Commission to Visit and Examine State Institutions*, \$31,800
- Massachusetts Institute of Technology, *Preserving Global Voices: Digitizing Endangered Language Recordings from the Kenneth L. Hale Papers*, \$36,151
- Peabody Essex Museum, *Austral Islands Field Recordings by Martin Brunor*, \$15,399
- Purdue University Archives and Special Collections, *Preserving the films and audio recordings of time and motion study pioneers Frank and Lillian Gilbreth*, \$26,142
- Ree & Jun Kaneko Foundation, *Preserving Creative Legacies: The Ree & Jun Kaneko Audiovisual Digitization Project*, \$21,313
- Regent University, *Preserving the Baptista Film Collection*, \$26,517
- Spelman College, *Lasting Legacies: Preserving and Providing Access to the Rich Audiovisual History of Spelman College*, \$49,995
- State Historical Society of Iowa, *Preserving Iowa's Natural History – Digitizing Iowa Conservation Commission Films*, \$18,971
- Strong National Museum of Play, *Digitizing the Anne D. Williams Collection: Preserving and Sharing the Historical Impact of Jigsaw Puzzles*, \$10,860
- Thornton Library, *Granville County's Black educators, interviewed by James Eddie McCoy*, \$15,180
- UBalt Foundation, *Preserving and Providing Access to Baltimore Television News Station WMAR, 1984-1993 (Phase Two)*, \$42,555
- University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA Library), *From Rashomon to Shakespeare: Preserving the Formative Years of East West Players*, \$37,073
- University of California, San Francisco (UCSF), *Selma Fraiberg's Films: Insights Into Child Development*, \$50,000
- University of Miami Libraries, *The Keystone to Justice: Preserving the Janet Reno Audiovisual Recordings*, \$27,750
- University of Nebraska Medical Center, *Preserving Minds: Digitizing Historic Psychiatric Films of the University of Nebraska Medical Center*, \$17,562
- University of Pittsburgh, *Preserving the "Let's Tell a Story" Radio Recordings*, \$25,946
- Virginia Commonwealth University Libraries, *Preserving the Films of Richmond Police Department Surveillance Records*, \$24,585
- William Way LGBT Community Center, *Reformatting the Gaydreams Radio Show Recordings*, \$24,450

AFFILIATES

CLIR and the DLF program establish collaborative relationships and cross-institutional initiatives with organizations that have similar missions in the pursuit of common goals. As a US-based 501(c)(3) organization, CLIR can serve as a stable fiscal or administrative home for organizations that may not need to be independent legal entities. Affiliates have their own governance and mission, while CLIR provides integrated services and access to tools, platforms, research, and expertise to reduce costs, create greater efficiencies, and allow affiliates to better serve their constituencies.

Affiliates (as of June 30, 2025)

- code{4}lib
- Institute for Liberal Arts Digital Scholarship (ILiADS)
- International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF)
- International Internet Preservation Consortium (IIPC)
- LD4 Community
- National Digital Stewardship Alliance (NDSA)
- Open Repositories
- Scholastic Commentaries and Texts Archive (SCTA)
- Shared Print Partnership
- South Asia Open Archives (SAOA)
- Weave: Journal of Library User Experience

PUBLICATIONS

In 2024-2025, CLIR published 3 titles commissioned through the **Pocket Burgundy** publication series. Through its work on the series, CLIR benefits from learning about pressing questions facing its constituencies while elevating new voices and promoting new ideas.

Archivist Actions, Abolitionist Futures: Reimagining Archival Practice Against Incarceration challenges long-held principles of archival practice by addressing the carceral underpinnings of the cultural professions. Drawing from their experiences working with collections documenting the lives and creativity of incarcerated individuals, authors reflect on how traditional archival methods fall short of providing respectful access to these materials.

Creating Ethical Temporary Positions in Archives: Best Practices and Case Studies examines why and how cultural organizations have come to rely so heavily on contingent positions to perform core operational work. Grounded in research including a literature review, survey findings, and case studies, their report offers guidelines on how to most ethically design, hire, and administer term-limited archival positions.

The Story of the Modern Seed Library: A Historical Analysis of Seed Saving, Its Evolution Through the Ages, and Its Current Impact on Community, Culture, and Connection explores the relationship between humans and seeds, from the first agricultural societies 12,000 years ago to the modern era of centralized agribusiness corporations. As genetic biodiversity in plant life collapses due to climate change, authors offer seed libraries as a community-centered service that libraries can provide to combat food insecurity while celebrating biodiversity.

REVENUE AND EXPENSES

For the 12 months to June 30, 2025

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

For the 12 months to June 30, 2025
with summarized financial information as of
June 30, 2024

Current Assets:	<i>Without Donor Restrictions</i>	<i>With Donor Restrictions</i>	<i>Total June 30, 2025</i>	<i>Total June 30, 2024</i>
Cash and cash equivalents	\$1,154,411	\$13,087,513	\$14,241,924	\$12,652,037
Investments	\$566,920		\$566,920	\$516,703
Prepaid expenses	\$37,351		\$37,351	\$93,062
Accounts receivable	\$635	\$5,942,482	\$5,943,117	\$5,641,354
Meeting deposits				\$9,798
Total Current Assets	\$1,759,317	\$19,029,995	\$20,789,312	\$18,912,954
Total Assets	\$1,759,317	\$19,029,995	\$20,789,312	\$18,912,954
Current Liabilities:				
Accounts payable	\$129,306	\$191,917	\$321,223	\$231,122
Compensated absences	\$145,957		\$145,957	\$113,627
Deferred registration revenue	\$171,186		\$171,186	\$157,639
Total Current Liabilities	\$446,449	\$191,917	\$638,366	\$502,388
Total Liabilities	\$446,449	\$191,917	\$638,366	\$502,388
Net Assets	\$1,312,868	\$18,838,078	\$20,150,946	\$18,410,566
Total Liabilities and Net Assets	\$1,759,317	\$19,029,995	\$20,789,312	\$18,912,954

SPONSORS AND MEMBERS

2024-2025

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- Alabama A & M University
- Alabama State University
- Albany State University
- Alcorn State University
- Allen University
- American Baptist College
- American University
- Amherst College+
- Arkansas Baptist College
- Atlanta University Center, Robert W. Woodruff Library*
- Bates College*
- Beloit College
- Benedict College
- Bennett College
- Berea College
- Bethune-Cookman University
- Bibliotheca Alexandrina+
- Binghamton University
- Bishop State Community College
- Bluefield State College
- Boston College*
- Bowdoin College*
- Bowie State University
- Brown University Library*
- Bryn Mawr College Libraries*
- California Digital Library*
- Carleton College
- Carthage College
- Casalini Libri
- Central State University
- Cheyney University of Pennsylvania
- Claflin University
- Clark Atlanta University
- Clemson University+
- Clinton College
- Coahoma Community College
- Coalition for Networked Information*
- Colgate University*
- College of Charleston
- College of the Holy Cross
- Colorado State University+
- Columbia University*
- Concordia University+
- Connecticut College
- Coppin State University
- Cornell University Libraries*
- Council of Independent Colleges
- Dartmouth College*
- Delaware State University
- Denmark Technical College
- Dillard University
- Duke University*
- Edward Waters College
- Elizabeth City State University
- Emory University*
- Fayetteville State University
- Fisk University
- Florida Agricultural and Mechanical University
- Florida Memorial University
- Florida State University+
- Fort Valley State University
- Gadsden State Community College
- George Mason University
- Georgetown University*
- Georgia Institute of Technology*
- Georgia State University+
- Getty Research Institute+
- Grambling State University
- Grinnell College*
- Hamilton College*

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- Hampton University
- Harris-Stowe State University
- Haverford College*
- HBCU Library Alliance+
- Howard University
- Huston-Tillotson University
- Indiana University*
- Interdenominational Theological Center
- Internet Archive+
- Iowa State University*
- ITHAKA+
- J. F. Drake State Community and Technical College
- Jackson State University
- Jarvis Christian College
- Jisc*
- Johns Hopkins University Libraries^
- Johnson C Smith University
- Kentucky State University
- Kenyon College*
- Lafayette College*
- Lane College
- Langston University
- Lawson State Community College
- Le Moyne-Owen College
- Library of Congress*
- Lincoln University
- Lincoln University Missouri
- Livingstone College
- Los Alamos National Laboratory+
- McMaster University*
- Meharry Medical College
- Metropolitan New York Library Council (METRO)+
- Miami University
- Michigan State University+
- Middle Tennessee State University*
- Middlebury College
- Miles College
- Mississippi Valley State University
- Morehouse College
- Morehouse School of Medicine
- Morgan State University
- Morris College
- Mount Holyoke College*
- National Gallery of Art+
- National Library of Medicine*
- New York Arts Resources Consortium+
- New York Public Library*
- New York University*
- Norfolk State University
- North Carolina A & T State University
- North Carolina Central University
- North Carolina State University Libraries*
- Northeastern University*
- Oakwood University
- Oberlin College+
- Occidental College*
- Oregon State University Libraries*
- Paine College
- Paul Quinn College
- Peabody Essex Museum Phillips Library+
- Pennsylvania State University*
- Philadelphia Museum of Art+
- Philander Smith College
- Prairie View A & M University
- Princeton Theological Seminary+
- Princeton University Library*
- Purdue University Library*
- Reed College*

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- Rhodes College*
- Rice University*
- Rockefeller Archive Center+
- Rockefeller University*
- Rust College
- Rutgers, the State University of New Jersey
- San Diego State University
- Savannah State University
- Science History Institute+
- Sewanee: The University of the South
- Shaw University
- Shelton State Community College
- Shorter College
- Simmons College of Kentucky
- Smith College*
- Smithsonian Institution*
- South Carolina State University
- Southern Methodist University*
- Southern University and A & M College
- Southern University at New Orleans
- Southern University at Shreveport
- Southern University Law Center
- Southwestern Christian College
- Spelman College
- St Philip's College
- St. Augustine's University
- St. Olaf College
- Stanford University^
- Stillman College
- Swarthmore College*
- Syracuse University*
- Talladega College
- Temple University Library*
- Tennessee State University
- Texas College
- Texas Southern University
- The Catholic University of America
- The Claremont Colleges*
- The Corning Museum of Glass+
- The George Washington University*
- The Huntington Library, Art Collections & Botanical Gardens+
- The Obama Foundation+
- The Ohio State University*
- Tougaloo College
- Trenholm State Community College
- Tufts University*
- Tulane University*
- Tuskegee University
- Union College*
- University at Albany*
- University of Alabama at Birmingham+
- University of Arizona Library*
- University of Arkansas at Pine Bluff
- University of Arkansas*
- University of British Columbia*
- University of Calgary*
- University of California, Berkeley*
- University of California, Irvine*
- University of California, Los Angeles*
- University of California, Riverside+
- University of California, San Diego Libraries*
- University of California, Santa Cruz+
- University of Chicago Library*
- University of Colorado at Boulder*
- University of Delaware Library*
- University of Denver*
- University of the District of Columbia
- University of the District of Columbia-David A Clarke School of Law

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- University of Georgia Libraries*
- University of Houston*
- University of Idaho+
- University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*
- University of Iowa Libraries+
- University of Kansas*
- University of Kentucky Libraries+
- University of Louisville+
- University of Maryland at College Park*
- University of Maryland Eastern Shore
- University of Massachusetts Libraries*
- University of Miami*
- University of Michigan*
- University of Minnesota Libraries*
- University of Nebraska-Lincoln*
- University of Nevada, Las Vegas Libraries+
- University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill*
- University of North Texas*
- University of Notre Dame*
- University of Oklahoma Libraries
- University of Oxford*
- University of Pennsylvania*
- University of Pittsburgh*
- University of Richmond*
- University of Rochester*
- University of South Carolina+
- University of South Florida*
- University of Southern California*
- University of Tennessee*
- University of Texas at Arlington*
- University of Texas at Austin*
- University of Toronto Library*
- University of Utah*
- University of the Virgin Islands
- University of the Virgin Islands-Albert A. Sheen
- University of Virginia*
- University of Washington*
- University of Wisconsin-Madison*
- University of Wyoming*
- Vanderbilt University*
- Vassar College Libraries*
- Villanova University*
- Virginia Commonwealth University*
- Virginia State University
- Virginia Tech*
- Virginia Union University
- Virginia University of Lynchburg
- Voorhees College
- Wake Forest University*
- Washington and Lee University Library*
- Washington University in St. Louis*
- Wayne State University+
- Wellesley College
- Wesleyan University*
- West Virginia State University
- West Virginia University Libraries*
- Whitman College+
- Wilberforce University
- Wiley College
- Williams College Libraries*
- Winston-Salem State University
- Xavier University of Louisiana
- Yale University Library*

FOUNDATION AND INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT

July 1, 2024 - June 30, 2025

- 4Science
- Adam Matthew Digital & Quartex Pelham House
- The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation
- East View Information Services
- Institute of Museum and Library Services
- Libnova
- LOCKSS Program
- Mellon Foundation
- Recollect CMS
- Tind Technologies
- Wikipedia Education

BOARD, 2024-2025

Guy Berthiaume (*Chair*)
Librarian and Archivist of Canada
Emeritus

Michele Casalini
Chief Executive Officer
Casalini Libri

Tess Davis
Executive Director
Antiquities Coalition

Mercedes de Vega Armijo
Director General Emerita
National Archives of Mexico

Laurence Engel
President Emerita
Bibliothèque nationale de France

Fenella France
Chief, Preservation Research and Testing
Division
Library of Congress

Charles Henry
President
CLIR

Anne Jarvis
Dean of Libraries and Robert H. Taylor
1930 University Librarian
Princeton University

Carol Mandel (*Vice Chair*)
Dean Emerita
New York University Division of
Libraries

Buhle Mbambo-Thata
University Librarian
National University of Lesotho

Ismail Rashid
Professor of History on the Marion
Musser Lloyd '32 Chair
Vassar College

Stephen Rhind-Tutt
President
Coherent Digital

Ben Vinson III
President Emeritus
Howard University

Sohair Wastawy
President
The Information Guild

John Price Wilkin (*Treasurer*)
CEO
Lyris

STAFF, 2024-2025

**denotes new staff joining July 1, 2024 - June 30, 2025*

Elizabeth Albert
John Boynton*
Sharon Burney
Jennifer Ferretti
Will Fisher*
Wayne Graham
Charles Henry
Olga Holownia
Martin Kalfatovic*
Louisa Kwasigroch
Jane Larson
Amy Lucko
Kayla Martin-Gant
Stacey Patton
Caitlin Perry
Alyson Pope
Dianeladia Ramirez
Jodi Reeves Eyre
Aliya Reich
Alice Rubin*
Julie Beroukas Snyder*
Sharon Weiss
Christa Williford

PRESIDENTIAL FELLOWS

JULY 1, 2024 - JUNE 30, 2025

Stephen Epstein

Former advisor

US State Department Bureau of Near Eastern Affairs

W. Joseph King

Past President

Lyon College

Carol Mandel

Dean Emerita

New York University Libraries

Presidential Fellows Emeriti

Kevin Fitzgerald (2021-2025)

Fenella France (2019-2021)

David Gift (2018-2022)

Herman Pabbruwe (2018-2022)

Elizabeth Waraksa (2018-2022)

Jacqueline Goldsby (2017-2022)

Michael Suarez (2015-2017)

Michael Edson (2014-2016)

John Unsworth (2014-2016)

Stephen Nichols (2013-2015)

Bethany Nowviskie (2013-2015)

G. Sayeed Choudhury (2009-2011)

Michael Keller (2007-2009)

Geneva Henry (2005)

Richard A. Detweiler (2003)

Denise Troll Covey (2000)

Angee Baker (2000)

Max Marmor (2000)

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www.clir.org
contact@clir.org